

NON-EXPLOSIVE SIMULATED BLAST LOADING OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH BEAMS

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SUMMARY

A dynamic loading method for simulating explosive blast was developed using a crushing foam projectile launched by a gas gun at velocities ranging from 30-60 m/s. This test method is used to load composite specimens to study the dynamic failure of carbon/epoxy sandwich structures. Such methods are desirable since they are easier and safer to implement than real explosive blast tests.

Keywords: composite sandwich, blast loading, non-explosive, dynamic failure, testing

INTRODUCTION

Advanced FRP composites usage in the construction of large load bearing ship structures has been increasing steadily over the past few decades (1–3). Concerns and major impediments to their use associated with structural fire integrity and resistance to damage caused by blast, however, have yet to be fully addressed (e.g. 4, 5). Dynamic behavior of composites, overall, has not been studied in any of the kind of depth as it has for metals and alloys, for example, and thus many outstanding issues remain concerning the response of FRP composites to the very high strain rates imposed by blast loading. Our concern is with the combined testing and analysis of blast induced deformation and failure of FRP composite ship structures at both the full-scale level of the entire ship structures as well as the testing and analysis at small scales for the purpose of documenting constitutive data and failure modes and data that may be used to calibrate failure models at high rates of loading. Specifically, our objectives herein are twofold: (i) the development of a non-explosive based dynamic loading methodology for documenting deformation and failure modes and for measuring materials oriented properties and failure parameters, and (ii) the implementation of this testing technique to excite various failure modes of specific interest in FRP composites subject to blast-like loading.

The methods must be capable of meeting requirements including (i) imposing realistic ranges of pressure and impulse vs. time history, i.e. those that are truly representative of actual blasts; (ii) be relatively inexpensive and time effective since for the purposes of collecting data used for the calibration and validation of material constitutive and failure models numerous tests are necessary; and (iii) be amenable to the comprehensive collection of data including local strain and deflection vs. time and visual observation of specimen response. Of course, developing a non-explosive methodology has the

advantages of allowing for these requirements to be fulfilled as well as providing a far higher degree of laboratory safety.

Our basic method makes use of high speed projectiles, characterized by tailored material and geometric designs, and launched in a gas-gun. These tailored projectiles are described below in detail along with their constituent materials. The gas-gun setup is described as well.

BLAST PRESSURE VS. TIME

Details about blast loading in the open literature have focused on the description of overpressure pulse measurements onto full-scale walls and onto smaller-scale test panels. A selection of these are summarized for the purpose of describing the range of pressures and duration of pulse that are relevant to the topic of blast loading onto structures.

Jacinto *et al.* (6) conducted a series of air-blast tests to measure overpressure pulses and dynamic response of plates for explosive charges ranging in mass from 0.8 to 10 kg located at 30 to 60 m from target plates of 1 to 1.5 m² in area. They measured pressure pulses which had an almost immediate rise to peak pressures in the 1-10 kPa range with pressures tapering-off over durations of up to 10 ms. Scherbatiuk and Rattanawangcharoen (7) conducted open air blast tests on free-standing soil-filled concertainer walls and measured pulses of similar shape and of magnitudes in the range 0.8 to 6 MPa and lasting for durations of 3 to 8 ms. Thus after peak pressures were attained, the pressures expectedly dropped off in the above mentioned time periods. In still other experiments, peak and overpressures pressures were measured by Houlston *et al.* (8) in the range 50 kPa to nearly 4 MPa for durations of 1-2 ms in for blasts onto test plates. Details of charge type and mass were not provided, but it is notable that at the higher pressures attained the durations were no longer than 1 ms. Davidson *et al.* (9) measured peak pressures in the 300 kPa range with durations of roughly 10 ms for blasts onto polymer-reinforced concrete masonry walls.

There are reports of blast induced pressures directly related to ship structures as the following examples illustrate. Slater (10) investigated blast-resistance of glass fiber reinforce plastic (GRP) composite panels for use in Naval ship structures. Up to full-scale test panels, with dimensions 2.7 m x 4.9 m, were subject to explosive blast loading. Measured pressure pulses reported had peak pressures of 105 to 405 kPa (classified as moderate and severe conditions, respectively) and durations of 50 to 100 ms for panel and beam specimens, and 200 ms for the full-scale test panel. Methods for investigating blast damage to composites by smaller-scale test specimens were reported on by Mouritz (11) who studied underwater blast loading onto relatively small (270 x 70 mm) stitched composite test specimens by suspending 30 or 50 g of explosive 1 m distance away from the specimen under water. These produced low and high intensity blast overpressures, with peak pressures reaching 13 and 25 MPa, respectively, as measured by a pressure sensor mounted onto the specimen surface. The pulses were roughly triangular in profile, with an almost equal rise and decay time, lasting 20 to 35 microseconds and were used to excite damage, via delamination cracking, in the test specimens. Surveys such as these, therefore, show that blast peak pressures of typical interest lie in a rather broad range of say, 0.5 to 10 MPa, with overpressure durations ranging from 0.5 to 10 ms or even higher. The work reported on herein is focused on dynamic loading of smaller-scale test specimens, namely beams and panels. Since these

specimens are typically an order of magnitude smaller in length-scale than full-size ship structures, higher magnitude pressures are needed in order to excite failure, thereby permitting detailed measurement of the material behavior of these test specimens. Of main interest, therefore, is the time-scale for which these pressure pulses are being applied to account for the strain-rate sensitive failure behavior of these materials. With the above comments concerning pulse duration in mind, and given the size of our small-scale specimens, we present cases characterized by pulse durations of ≤ 2 ms.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Pressure Pulse Generating Projectile (PPGP)

Non-explosive based dynamic loading is achieved by the launching of a “soft” projectile using a 79 mm bore gas gun. The ultimate goal was to fire a projectile with the capability of producing a known pressure pulse to excite failure in composite panel targets of varying geometry and boundary conditions. The soft projectile, referred to as the pressure-pulse generating projectile (PPGP), shown in Fig. 1, is constructed of a two-part liquid cast crushable rigid urethane foam mounted in front of a 663 g aluminum body. The projectile has a 78.9 mm diameter and is constructed from one of the three rigid urethane foams of nominal density 80, 160, and 240 kg/m³ (5, 10, and 15 lb/ft³). The aluminum body is used to impart momentum and to crush down the foam, as well as hold the V-seals that produce a low-friction gas-tight seal between the projectile and barrel. Aft of the body are lightweight flexible fins to provide flight stability to the projectile. Between the foam and the aluminum body is a liquid-cast dense urethane plastic interface section that reinforces the connection of the crushable foam to the body. Without this dense plastic section, the foam would locally crush at this location where it contacts the aluminum body.

Figure 1. Crushable Foam Projectile

Polymer foam was chosen as a crushable media due to the desirable compressive stress vs. strain behavior these materials have been show to exhibit (12–14). Specifically, under large compressive crushing strain, the polymer foams showed an almost elastic-perfectly plastic response. The magnitude of the “yielding” stress is directly controllable by selection of the density of foam.

Fabrication of the projectile consists of molding the crushable foam and plastic interface section as one continuous unit. The process begins by mixing (two liquid parts) and pouring the rigid urethane foam into the cylindrical mold. The resulting cylindrical shape is trimmed to a length of 90 mm before it is placed back into the mold and the liquid urethane casting plastic is poured in. This non-expanding plastic fills up the rest of the mold creating the dense plastic interface geometry (see Fig. 1) which then inserts snugly into a socket on the forward face of the aluminum projectile body.

The PPGPs were launched using the gas gun shown in Fig. 2. This gun has a 79 mm inner diameter bore, 2.29 m long barrel, and is capable of firing up to 79 mm diameter projectiles to velocities over 200 m/s. The gas gun is powered by bottled nitrogen gas that pressurizes a tank connected to the end of the barrel. The tank pressure is released into the breech of the gun via a fast-opening valve actuated with helium gas. The projectile passes through a velocity measuring system composed of two laser photogates prior to impacting the target of interest.

Figure 2. Gas Gun and Force Measurement Bar Systems

Pressure pulses produced by the PPGP were measured by a dynamic force measurement bar (FMB). This apparatus (see Figs. 2 and 3) consists of a 3.5 m long hollow aluminum bar of 76.2 mm outer diameter having an end-cap onto which the PPGP impacts. Stress waves traveling down the bar are measured by two strain gages located 457 mm from the end cap and placed on opposite sides of the bar. From these dynamic strain measurements, the applied pressure (force) pulse can be determined. A Vishay 2310B strain signal conditioner is used for the strain gage excitation and signal amplification (10X gain used). A PicoScope 3424 12-bit digital oscilloscope was used for high speed data acquisition. For visual observation of the projectile's behavior, a Phantom V4.2 high speed camera was used to record the projectile in flight and during the impact event at a frame rate of 1000 to 4000 frames per second. Tests were conducted to characterize each projectile at nominally 30.5 m/s (100 ft/s) for the three foam densities. The gas gun was compressed to 345 kPa (50 psi) to achieve this speed.

Figure 3. Test Apparatus Setup

Composite Test Specimen Description

Tests were also conducted with composite laminate specimens manufactured by ManTech. The specimens were sandwich panels of a carbon fiber laminated facesheets and end-grain balsa wood core. The facesheets are composed of high-strength carbon fiber (Toray T700) in woven form impregnated with Vinylester resin via a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. A thinner 4.32 mm facesheet was located on one side of the 50.8 mm thick balsa core, and a thicker 13.97 mm facesheet on the other was used for beam test specimens. The panels were cut into 79 mm by 305 mm specimens. Since the immediate goal was to examine the strength of the facesheets themselves, the panels were cut such that the resulting specimen consisted of the carbon fiber laminate and about 13 mm of balsa remaining attached to the facesheet. This was done so as not to risk damage to the facesheet since the stiffness and strength of the balsa is negligible relative to the carbon fiber laminate. At the beam ends, the balsa was carefully removed completely from the facesheet to allow mounting of the specimens in the test frame such that clamped end conditions can be achieved, exposing 250 mm free span of the beam.

RESULTS

Impact onto FMB

Initial tests were conducted to observe the flight characteristics of the projectile as it is desired to achieve a normal-contact impact to uniformly compress the projectile. Observation by high-speed video shows the flight path to be straight and stable, with no gross tilting or even spin of the projectile. Upon confirmation of stable flight, the velocity measurement system was re-installed, and impacts onto the FMB were carried out to characterize the pressure pulses produced by the different foam densities. Fig. 4 shows the PPGP impacting the FMB at an incoming velocity of 30.81 m/s. The projectile is observed to strike the FMB end cap squarely and then crush as it imparts a pressure pulse. Typical pressure pulse measurements for the three foam densities tested are plotted in Figs. 5 to 7 for projectiles launched at a nominal velocity of 30.5 m/s.

Figure 4. PPGP Impacting FMB at 30.81 m/s; 160 kg/m³ Density Foam

Repetitions of these test conditions show the projectiles to produce repeatable, consistent, pressure pulses. It can be clearly observed that higher foam densities result in higher peak pressures, and the lowest density foam exhibited longer pulse duration. Note that the pulse for the 80 kg/m³ foam projectiles actually exceed the duration of measurement capability of the FMB which is 1.1 ms (time for stress wave to travel to far end of the bar and return to the strain gage location).

Figure 5. Pressure History for 80 kg/m³ Projectile at 30.5 m/s

Figure 6. Pressure History for 160 kg/m³ Projectile at 30.5 m/s

Figure 7. Pressure History for 240 kg/m³ Projectile at 30.5 m/s

Fig. 8 summarizing the peak pressures measured for these tests shows a linear relationship between pressure and density of the foam. Tuning of the pressure pulse is possible by selection of foam density. The magnitude of the pressure pulse is controlled by the compressive crushing strength of the foam which is directly related to the foam's density. The quasi-static compressive stress vs. strain behavior for the three foam densities has been measured to display a nearly elastic-perfectly plastic relationship. Comparison with the peak pressures developed by the PPGP shows the peak pressures to be on the order of two times the quasi-static compressive strength. It should be noted that these compressive strengths are related to much slower strain rate (10^{-1} s^{-1}) than the strain rates associated with deformation of the flying PPGP as it impacts onto the FMB. It is hypothesized that the higher pressures are due to viscoelastic behavior of the foam and dynamic effects as the PPGP initially impacts the FMB.

Figure 8. Peak Pressure vs. Foam Density

Impact onto Composite Beams

Once the projectile has been characterized and known to produce repeatable and tailorable pressure vs. time pulses, the PPGP was used to excite damage in thick (13.97 mm) composite beams. Fig. 9 shows a close-up view of the projectile as it impacts the beam. Only the center portion of the beam's span is shown in this view. Large deformations can be observed in a predominantly bending mode. The compressive strength of composites is typically lower than the tensile strength, and thus initial failures were observed to occur on the front-face of the beam in the vicinity of the impact location. Fig. 10 shows initial damage to the near-surface plies produced from impacts by the 160 kg/m³ density foam projectiles at 45.7 m/s velocity.

Figure 9. Close-Up View of PPGP Impacting Composite Beam

Figure 10. Beam Specimens Impacted by 160 kg/m³ Foam Fired at 45.7 m/s

The amount of damage visible in these figures is minimal (i.e., it thus is classified as initial damage) and can be seen by the light-colored cracking patterns on the impact-face. This whitening is actually produced by the localized debonding of the stainless steel surface mesh (mounted for lightning and electromagnetic shielding purposes) as

the bending-induced compressive failure cracks develop. A slightly raised surface is also visible at the impact face, which is typical of compressive failure in fiber-reinforced composites due to the presence of delamination. The two separate test specimens show a high degree of repeatability in the excitation of damage initiation. Higher velocity (61.0 m/s) developed even greater amount of damage (see Fig. 11), including visible frontside compressive failure (fiber fracture) and significant delamination at multiple planes through the laminate thickness. Backside tensile fiber failure is also visible upon close examination. The damage induced by these examples are primarily bending failure modes. As expected, compressive failure at the impact side develops first. By varying the thickness and span of the specimens, excitation of transverse shear vs. bending dominated failure modes is possible, while using this methodology of dynamic load application via the use of the PGPPs.

Figure 11. Beam Specimen Impacted by 160 kg/m^3 Foam Fired at 61.0 m/s

CONCLUSIONS

A description of the development of a flying “soft” projectile used for simulating dynamic blast loading pulses, for use to test “small-scale” composite specimens, was described herein. The pressure pulse generating projectiles, i.e., PPGP, were found to produce pressure pulses of desirable profile. While the magnitude of these pulses is higher than what would occur in air-blast situations, such pressures are necessary in order to excite failure in the small-sized test specimens of interest. The magnitude of the pressure pulse was found to be controllable by selection of foam density. A linear relationship was observed between peak pressure and density of the foam. The peak pressure magnitude was also observed to be directly related to foam compressive crushing strength, with peak pressures being roughly twice the quasi-static compressive strength of the corresponding density foam. Finally, the PPGP was applied to excite damage in thick composite beams and was found to be capable of repeatedly exciting the same initial failure mode for the same incoming projectile conditions (foam density and velocity). Extensive bending-induced failure was produced with higher velocity impacts. Future activity will entail applying the PPGP to more thoroughly study the formation of damage modes via various beam spans to excite shear vs. bending dominated failure. Strain gage measurement and analysis of high speed video will provide quantitative data monitoring the specimen response during dynamic loading. Dynamic loading and failure of sandwich panels will also be investigated using the test methodology described herein. Ultimately, the goal is to generate a database of damage modes and damage levels, and use these data to support the development of failure

models within a dynamic numerical simulation framework. These data and observations will play an essential role in the validation of such simulation tools.

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